

Henry 2022, Tri-allelic SNPs outperform functional candidates for biochemical profiles in Cannabis, Journal of Brief Ideas

Clusters	α -Pinene	β -Myrcene	Limonene	Terpinolene	Linalool	β -Caryophyllene	Total monoterpene	Total terpene
k1 THC	0.078%	0.081%	0.310%	0.005%	0.034%	0.207%	0.811%	1.302%
k2 THC	0.15%	0.37%	0.31%	0.07%	0.09%	0.21%	1.29%	1.74%
k3 CBD/THC	0.03%	0.50%	0.14%	0.01%	0.04%	0.11%	0.85%	1.23%
k4 CBD	0.19%	0.52%	0.09%	0.01%	0.03%	0.04%	0.98%	1.27%

Clusters	Total CBDV (0.867)	Total CBG (0.878)	Total CBD (0.877)	Total THCv (0.867)	Total THC (0.877)	Total CBC (0.877)	Total cannabinoids
k1 THC	0.007%	0.593%	0.057%	0.107%	12.261%	0.424%	15.288%
k2 THC	0.007%	0.708%	0.667%	0.176%	13.672%	0.416%	17.767%
k3 CBD/THC	0.043%	0.448%	8.858%	0.028%	4.537%	0.557%	16.428%
k4 CBD	0.042%	0.303%	10.915%	0.007%	0.471%	0.566%	13.956%

NJ tree of 87 genotypes at 9 SNPs

PCA of 87 genotypes at 9 SNPs

Diversity indices

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PCA of 58 genotypes at 3mc SNPs

NJ tree of 58 genotypes at 3mc SNPs

NJ tree of 58 genotypes at triallelic SNP

PCA of 58 genotypes at triallelic SNPs

PKref	1	184	234	296	Sesqui61	myr048	myrc4
(THC) Lemon Love	1	AC	AG	TA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Lemon Sherbet	1	AC	AG	C/T	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Platinum Jelly Punc	1	AC	AG	C/T	NA	NA	NA
3CSG324C	1	AC	AG	C/T	AA	G/A	G/G
AutoAK47C23SRR32944	1	AC	AA	T/T	G/G	AA	NA
Cannabinoic223SRR3294	1	A/T	NA	T/T	AA	G/A	NA
Chem91C14SRR329443	1	AC	AA	T/T	G/A	G/A	G/C
CitrixSRR10578277	1	AC	AG	TA	AA	G/A	G/C
CSPKSL	1	AC	AG	TA	AA	G/A	G/C
EK56SRP0	1	A/A	AG	T/T	AA	G/A	G/C
G13C20SRR3294442.1	1	AC	AA	C/T	G/A	G/A	G/C
GoldenGoatC55SRR321	1	AC	AG	T/T	G/G	G/A	G/C
HarloxSRR10578266	1	AC	AG	C/T	G/A	AA	G/G
HarjuanaSRR10578253	1	A/A	AG	C/T	G/A	AA	C/C
LowRyderC24SRR32944	1	A/A	AA	T/T	AA	G/A	G/C
MothersMik5SRR105782	1	AC	AG	C/T	AA	AA	C/C
OGKushC54SRR329447	1	AC	A/A	C/T	AA	AA	NA
RedEyeOGSRR1057828	1	AC	AG	C/T	AA	AA	C/C
TahoeOGSRR10578283	1	AC	AG	C/T	G/A	AA	G/C
(BAL)ANCED1 Lemon Gari	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) 33*	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Banana Cake	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Bananium	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Burmese Blueberry	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Divine Banana	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Granddaddy Purple	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) MeatHead	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Nantico	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) S89K2	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
(THC) Super sherbet	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
2CSG324C	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	G/C
AlghanKushC2SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	C/C
AlghanKush4C5SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	G/G	AA	C/C
AlghanKush5C6SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	G/G	AA	C/C
AlghanKush6C4SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	G/G	AA	C/C
AscanThunderCuck47	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	NA
ArcataTrainwreckSRR10	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	G/C
Back84SRR10578284	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	AA	G/C
BackBeautySRR1057821	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
BlueberryChocoCake04	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	G/C
BlueberryDJC48SRR325	2	CA	GA	CA	G/G	G/G	G/C
Chem91SRR10578287	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
Chocoopie1C46SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	NA
C312016C3SRR10578	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
GrapeStomperSRR10578	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	AA	G/G
GrapeApe1C44SRR3294	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	G/C
HeadChesaSRR105782	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
JackHeret1C27SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/G	C/C
JamaicanLon41SRR105	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	AA	G/C
JamaicanLon42SRR105	2	CA	GA	CA	G/G	G/A	G/C
JamaicanLon43SRR105	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
JamaicanLon44SRR105	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	G/A	G/C
JamaicanLon45SRR105	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	G/A	G/C
JamaicanLon46SRR105	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	G/C
JamaicanLon3FatherSR1	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	G/A	G/C
JamaicanLon3MotherPC	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	AA	G/C
JamaicanLon3MayerSR	2	CA	GA	CA	G/A	G/A	G/C
JLSRR10019825	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
LebaneseC18SRR32944	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
LibertyHazeC50SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	G/C
MastersKushSRR1057825	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	G/C
SanLackSRR10578255	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	G/A	C/C
Skunk1C53SRR3294477	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	C/C
SourDieselSRR1057828	2	CA	GA	CA	AA	AA	C/C
TangerineHazeC51SRR	2	CA	GA	CA	G/G	AA	G/C
WhiteWidow1A2SRR329	2	CA	GA	CA	NA	NA	C/C
(BAL)ANCED1 Royal Medix	3	C/T	G/T	AC	NA	NA	NA
(BAL)ANCED1 Dance Wor	3	C/T	G/T	AC	NA	NA	NA
(BAL)ANCED1 High	3	C/T	G/T	AC	NA	NA	NA
3FSG484C	3	C/T	G/T	CC	AA	AA	G/C
DomnesiaSRR10578250	3	C/T	G/T	CC	AA	AA	C/C
DurbanPoison1C16SRR	3	C/T	G/T	CC	G/A	AA	C/C
SourTsunamiSRR105782	3	C/T	G/T	A/A	AA	AA	C/C
(CBD) Blue Hawaiian	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	NA	NA	NA
(CBD) Kandy Kush	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	NA	NA	NA
(CBD) Special	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	NA	NA	NA
(CBD) NN	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	NA	NA	NA
(CBD) Train	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	NA	NA	NA
(CBD) C67	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	NA	NA	NA
3CSG4841	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	AA	G/A	G/G
CBDXRHR3850	4	T/T	T/T	A/A	G/G	G/G	G/G

